

CATALYTIC CONDENSATION OF BIOBASED MOLECULES FOR JET FUEL SYNTHESIS

Karla Dussan^{1*}, Martin Peters², Stefania M. Scalzullo³, Ben Smith³, André van Zomeren¹, Xavier Baucherel³, Axel Kraft², Jaap W. van Hal¹

¹ Biobased and Circular Technologies Group, Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research – TNO, Westerduinweg 3, 1755 LE Petten, Netherlands

² Fraunhofer UMSICHT, Osterfelder Straße 3, D-46047 Oberhausen, Germany

³ Johnson Matthey, Reading, UK

ABSTRACT: The present work evaluates a process for the production of renewable jet fuel hydrocarbons using biobased precursors derived from 2nd generation biomass hemicellulose. A set of promising basic solid formed catalysts was benchmarked in lab-scale continuous fixed bed reactors to evaluate their catalytic performance in the cross-condensation of furfural and acetone and the self-condensation of cyclopentanone at two different temperature regimes. For the low temperature liquid process (80-120 °C), a hydrotalcite and a metal-organic-framework catalyst were most active and stable up to 53 h on stream, with high conversions (> 85 %) and favouring the formation of C13 over C8 products. For the high temperature gas-phase process (280-360 °C), a metal doped alumina catalyst was most active, with stable conversion (40-45 %) and a product distribution favouring C10 over C15 molecules. The two process regimes (low and high temperature) can provide flexibility in the production of biobased hydrocarbons for use in the aviation sector. Catalyst deactivation was observed due to strong carbon adsorption; however, most active materials could be regenerated via calcination. Future work will focus on the overall stability of these regenerated catalysts and the successive hydrotreatment of the condensation products.

Keywords: liquid biofuel, catalytic conversion, renewable jet fuel, fixed bed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aviation sector currently contributes to 2.5% of the total CO₂ global emissions [1]. The contribution of aviation to emissions per capita are quite large, especially for high income countries. Ambitious sustainability targets have been setup for and by the aviation sector. For instance, the ReFuelEU Aviation initiative aims to set increasing targets of sustainable aviation fuel shares at EU airports [2] or the IATA's net zero commitment by 2050 [3]. Some of the currently available options for certified sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) either rely on scarce and geographically dispersed feedstocks (e.g. HVO/HEFA from used cooking oil, animal fats) or on less sustainable first generation biomass (e.g. edible crops) which cannot cover the increasing fuel demand. European SAF demand is estimated to be 28 million tonnes by 2050 compared to the current 0.2 million tonnes of SAF produced today [4]. The H2020 HIGFLY project therefore aims to develop the next generation of technologies for the production of sustainable aviation fuels from abundant and sustainable biomass feedstocks or second generation (2G) biomass. HIGFLY develops a combination of technologies that produces kerosene hydrocarbons via biobased oxygenated precursors derived from 2G carbohydrates.

Furanic molecules, furfural and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, have been investigated in aldol-condensation process at lab scale with other (potentially) bio-based molecules, such as acetone, methyl isobutyl ketone, pentanones, 2-methylfuran, as cross-linking reagents. This path can potentially yield condensed oxygenated hydrocarbons with eight to 20 carbons (C8 to C20) [5, 6]. A large number of these studies have considered as catalysts mineral bases, mainly NaOH and KOH, but also hydroxides from alkali-earth metals and carbonates, as well as transition metal chlorides (e.g. FeCl₃, CoCl₂, NiCl₂). In general, this approach has the disadvantage of relying on high catalyst concentrations that make recyclability difficult. To address this, numerous studies have focused on the assessment of heterogeneous catalysts, covering a great variety of metal oxides, hydrotalcites (Mg-Al, Co-Al, Li-Al), ion exchange

resins and modified carbon materials [7]. Studies employing metal oxides used temperatures between 60 and 180 °C and reaction times that ranging from 2 to 8 h. Conversions and yields were diverse, where CaO, MgO, ZnO and combinations thereof have reported the highest conversions/yields. Hydrotalcites are used mostly between 130 and 170 °C for reaction times that vary between 6 to 20 h. Conversions are rather moderate, however, ranging from 20 to 100% and yields varying from 20 to 82%. The most promising of this type of materials are MgAl-hydrotalcites [8-10].

Alternatively, direct gas-phase catalytic condensation of alcohols and ketones, which can be produced via sugar fermentation, has also been reported as a viable option for jet fuel production [11-13]. In this route, the process is performed at high temperatures (> 300 °C) using a carbon catalyst loaded with inorganic active compounds and without transition or noble metals.

In both these routes, jet fuel/kerosene like molecules are obtained after further hydrotreatment of the condensed intermediate molecules, since the products are still partly oxygenated. All these studies evaluate the condensation and hydrotreatment reactions in batch. Validating strategies for continuous operation, as opposed to batch, using furfural and other biobased oxygenates is essential for the development of scalable and sustainable jet fuel technology. Additionally, an important aspect in the properties of the condensed intermediates is their relative low volatility and high melting/boiling points. This is therefore a challenge in the development of scalable jet fuel technology through these routes. Either a solvent or high temperatures (50-160 °C) are required to maintain condensed intermediates (>C8) in the liquid phase.

The scalability of the production of biobased jet fuel from furfural and cyclopentanone is evaluated as part of the H2020 HIGFLY project. The concept is based on two stages: (1) catalytic condensation to produce aldol products from the biobased precursors with the target number of carbons (C8-C15); and (2) hydrotreatment to upgrade the aldol products to saturated hydrocarbons. In the present work, we report the performance of pelletised/extrudate catalysts in the condensation reaction

step at low temperature (80-120 °C, liquid phase) and high temperature (280-360 °C, gas phase). Catalyst activity and product yields were evaluated over time under flow in fixed bed reactors. The stability of the catalysts during the process was also evaluated and strategies for catalyst regeneration were developed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Toluene (technical grade, 99 %), furfural (synthesis grade, 98 %), acetone (technical grade, 99 %), cyclopentanone (synthesis grade, 99 %) and 1-propanol (synthesis grade, 99 %) were purchased and used without further treatment. Commercial standards for chromatographic calibrations were purchased as follows: C8 standard was purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific, C13 standard was purchased from Key Organics (UK), C10 standards from abcr (Germany). All gases are supplied by Linde GmbH, Gases Division.

In the HIGFLY framework, Johnson & Matthey synthesised the following formed catalysts: A hydrotalcite type 3x3 pellet (referred to as HT2), zirconia-based metal organic framework catalyst (referred to as MOF808-ext), a metal-doped alumina 2 mm capillary extrudate (referred to as mdAl₂O₃-ext) and a second metal-doped alumina prepared by incipient wetness on trilobe 1.3 mm extrudates (referred to as mdAl₂O₃-tri). A commercially available alumina shaped carrier 3x3 mm cylindrical pellet (Sasol Germany GmbH) with an indicative composition of 24% wt MgO, 56% wt Al₂O₃ and 20% wt K₂CO₃ (Mg/Al molar ratio 0.54) was used as benchmark base catalyst and is further referred to as KMG30.

2.2 Low temperature cross condensation of furfural and acetone

The cross-condensation of furfural and acetone was carried out in a fixed-bed reactor system comprised of a jacketed tubular reactor (2.21 cm ID x 25.16 cm H) heated electrically, a feed section with two feed HPLC pumps, a N₂ feed gas section, a liquid-gas separator, and a product sampling and collection section. For these tests, the tubular reactor was packed with silica carbide (0.7 mm particle size, inert) in the inlet section of the heated zone, followed by 20 g of the formed catalyst (particle size 250-500 μm), and further covered with an upper layer of silica carbide. The catalysts were pretreated at indicated temperatures and time (Table I) under 100 mL_N/min N₂. After treatment, the reactor was set at the working temperature and pressure (100 or 120 °C and 30 barg) and then filled up with the reaction feed. A solution of 7.5% wt acetone and furfural in toluene was used as feed, with a molar ratio 2:1 furfural to acetone. Feed flow was set to provide a weight hourly space velocity (WHSV) of 1 g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹.

Table I: Pre-treatment conditions of catalysts

Catalysts	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)
KMG30	300	3
HT2	300	5
MOF808	Not applicable	Not applicable
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -ext	120	3
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -tri	120	3

After 50-55 h of time on stream (TOS), the pressure in

the installation is reduced, the feed pump turned off and reactor was flushed with N₂, toluene and again N₂, consecutively. The spent catalysts were removed, sieved and further characterised.

2.3 High temperature self-condensation of cyclopentanone

The self-condensation of cyclopentanone was carried out in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor system. The liquid feed was pumped with a HPLC pump into an evaporator. The evaporator was electrically heated and vaporized and superheated the feed to 300 °C. The vapour feed flowed through trace heated tubes into the fixed-bed reactor which is a stainless-steel tube with 21 mm inner diameter. The mass of the tested catalyst was about 20 g. The reactor was placed in a furnace, which provided the reaction temperature of 280 to 360 °C. The temperature was subsequently increased during the catalyst testing. The product mixture was condensed by air cooling and collected in a bottle. Both the bottle containing the feed mixture and the product bottle were weighed to evaluate the mass balance. The liquid samples were analysed via GC-FID/MS to quantify the concentration of not converted educts and products. The gaseous products were analysed with an at-line GC-FID/TCD to evaluate the amount of light hydrocarbons and permanent gases formed as side-products in the condensation reaction.

The feed was a mixture of 75 mol-% cyclopentanone and 25 mol-% n-octane. The n-octane was used as a solvent to avoid clogging due to crystallisation of large product molecules. Before starting the feed the catalyst was pre-treated at reaction temperature for 2 h in N₂ atmosphere.

2.3 Analytical methods

For the determination of furfural, acetone and condensation products from low temperature experiments, a HPLC column (Accucore C30 (150 mm x 4.6 mm, particle size 2.6 μm) and guard column (50 mm) were used. For the method, two eluents are used, eluent A: 0.05% TFA in water; and eluent B: acetonitrile. A gradient eluent was used as follows: 0-5 min, 10% eluent B + 90% eluent A, isocratic; 5-20 min, 10% to 75% eluent B, 90 to 25% eluent A; 20-25 min, 75% eluent B + 25% eluent A, isocratic. Peak assignment was confirmed with DAD 200-600 nm using a custom library, while quantification was performed with the UV signal at 254 nm. For this method, samples are diluted in water and acetonitrile, respectively for the measurement of acetone and the other analytes.

For determination of cyclopentanone and condensation products from high temperature experiments, GC-FID combined with mass spectrometry was used. When the liquid product contained two liquid phases the samples were homogenized using 1-propanol. For the analysis a gas chromatograph (Type 8890, Agilent) was used in combination with a mass spectrometer (Type 5977C, Agilent). For the separation a HP5ms column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm, J&W Agilent) was used. Helium (5.0 quality) was used as carrier gas. For the FID, hydrogen (5.0 quality) and synthetic hydrocarbon-free air (GC quality) were used. The quantification was performed by using the FID signal. Further substances are identified using the MS data. For further semi-quantitative or qualitative calculations, the peak area of the FID signal is used.

Specific surface area of the catalysts were characterised via Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method.

For this, 200-300 mg of this material was weighed into a 6 mm sample cell with a filler rod, and degassed at 300 °C under vacuum conditions. The actual outgassing time per sample was several hours. All measurements and degassing were performed on an Autosorb iQ-C from Quantachrome. A complete isotherm was measured by nitrogen adsorption. For MOF808 catalysts, degassing was performed at 120 °C.

The CO₂ temperature programmed desorption (CO₂-TPD) was carried out using an AMI-300 supplied by Altamira Instruments. About 70-100 mg sample were placed in a 1/4" quartz glass U-tube and kept in place with quartz wool. The analytical procedure consisted of four steps. First the sample was pre-treated at a material specific temperature (as indicated in Table I) and flushed with helium. After cooling down, the sample was treated with pure CO₂ at 30 °C for 1 h. The third step was the temperature programmed desorption. After flushing out excess CO₂ with helium, the sample was ramp-heated to a material specific temperature with 10 K min⁻¹ in a constant helium flow. The fourth step was a CO₂ pulse calibration for quantitative analysis of CO₂ uptake.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Condensation reactions in the scope of this work included the cross-condensation of furfural (FUR) and acetone (ACE) and the self-condensation of cyclopentanone (CPO). The first route leads to aldol products 4-(2-furyl)-3-buten-2-one (C8) and 1,5-di(furan-2-yl)penta-1,4-dien-3-one (C13), see Figure 1. The second route can potentially form various forms of self-condensation products such as 2-cyclopentylcyclopentan-1-one (C10) and 2,5-dicyclopentylcyclopentanone (C15), see Figure 2. Initially, catalysts were screened using the first route as a model process for the selection of most active materials and the development of their formed structures for use in fixed bed reactors. The following sections present the findings in screening formed catalysts in the two reaction regimes under continuous flow.

Figure 1: Cross-condensation of furfural and acetone.

Figure 2: Self-condensation of cyclopentanone.

3.1 Catalysts formation and properties

A wide variety of catalysts in powder form were initially screened in the selected reaction of ACE and FUR cross-condensation in liquid phase (data not shown). From this work, three types of catalysts were found to be most active: An Al-Mg hydrotalcite (HT2), a zirconia-based metal organic framework catalyst (MOF808), and a metal-

doped alumina (mdAl₂O₃). The HT2 material was later formed into pellets using alumina binders; while the MOF808 catalyst was formed into capillary extrudates using cellulose and hydrated aluminium silicate as binders. The mdAl₂O₃ catalyst was prepared via two methods: via extrusion into capillaries using cellulose and fibres as binders followed by calcination (mdAl₂O₃-ext) and via metal impregnation of alumina trilobe pellets (mdAl₂O₃-tri). Formed catalysts are shown in Figure 3. In addition, a commercial alumina pellet (KMG30) was also used in the screening activities.

Figure 3: (a) MOF-808 extrudate; (b) hydrotalcite HT-2 pellets; (c) metal-doped alumina trilobes.

Table II shows the surface area and basicity of the synthesised pellets. Metal content of the materials is not reported for propriety reasons. Surface area of the materials varied between 88 and 374 m²/g, the highest for the MOF808 material and lowest for the hydrotalcite-type materials (KMG30 and HT2). The low temperature basicity defined as the CO₂ that desorbs at temperature below 200 °C was lowest for the MOF808 material, followed by the mdAl₂O₃ catalysts and highest in the hydrotalcites (HT2 and KMG30). In particular, due to the composition and properties of MOF808, the catalyst is not suitable for high temperature treatment above 200 °C; therefore no high temperature basicity (200-500 °C) is reported for this catalyst. Furthermore, MOF808 was not used in tests of high temperature self-condensation of cyclopentanone under flow. For high temperature basicity, the materials showed an opposite trend: hydrotalcites had lower CO₂ uptake than the mdAl₂O₃ materials, in particular KMG30 with the lowest CO₂ uptake.

Table II: Properties of formed catalysts: BET surface area and basicity in terms of CO₂ uptake

Catalysts	BET surface area (m ² /g)	CO ₂ uptake <200 °C (μmol/g)	CO ₂ uptake 200-500 °C (μmol/g)
KMG30	88	96	210
HT2	94	89	524
MOF808	374	5.7	n.a.
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -ext	172	42	786
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -tri	197	62	709

The formed catalysts were either used as is (self-condensation of cyclopentanone at high temperature) or in reduced particle size (cross-condensation of furfural and acetone at low temperature).

3.2 Low temperature cross condensation of furfural and acetone

Tests to compare the performance of the catalyst were performed at either 100 or 120 °C, WHSV 1 g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹, 7.5 wt-% acetone (ACE) and furfural (FUR) in toluene and molar ratio of 2:1 FUR:ACE. Samples from the outlet of the reactor were taken over time. Figure 4 shows the conversion and yields attained at the initial stages of the experiment, that is time on stream (TOS) around 3-24 h. The initial activity of the catalysts was relatively similar leading to high conversions of ACE and FUR (> 85 %). The total yield of C8 and C13 products was high for most catalysts (90-94 %); except for the HT2 catalyst. The ratio of C8 to C13 also varied from catalyst to catalyst and throughout time. For the initial activity, C13/C8 molar ratio was between 3 and 11, except for the HT2 catalyst which formed predominantly the C13 product.

Figure 4: Initial conversion of FUR and ACE to C8 and C13 products.

The various catalysts showed distinct activities throughout time. At 120 °C and WHSV 1 g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹, the catalysts MOF808 and KMG30 were stable up to 53 h (end of tests), meaning steady conversions and yields were measured during the tests. Figure 5 shows the conversion and yields achieved throughout the test with KMG30 as an example. For KMG30, C8 and C13 yields increased during the first 5 h of the tests and remained steady until 53 h. MOF808 gave relatively stable FUR and ACE conversions since the start of the test, being lower than with KMG30, in average 68 % and 72 %, respectively. The molar ratio of C13 to C8 with these catalysts varied between 2 and 3.5.

On the other hand, the catalytic activity of HT2 and mdAl₂O₃ catalysts decreased gradually during the cross-condensation tests. As an example, Figure 6 shows the conversions and yields measured using mdAl₂O₃-ext catalyst at different TOS. With this catalyst, high conversions and yields were only observed at TOS 3 h, then decreased gradually reaching 12 % FUR conversion at TOS 53 h. During deactivation, it was seen that the conversion and the yield of C13 product decreases; however, the yield of C8 product increased slightly over time until TOS 30 h and then started to decrease.

Figure 5: Conversion of furfural and yields of C8 and C13 product molecules depending on TOS with KMG30 at 120 °C.

The HT2 and mdAl₂O₃-tri catalysts showed similar deactivation behaviours as mdAl₂O₃-ext. Deactivation of HT2 catalyst occurred more rapidly, becoming completely unactive after 39 h. Through the tests, the spent catalysts had gained a dark colour (dark brown to black) that showed organic deposition from the reactant/products onto their surface (Figure 7). Spent catalysts were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (data not shown) to assess whether the materials could be regenerated by thermal treatment. From these tests, a calcination temperature of 500 °C was selected to remove the carbon depositions on the catalysts. Since the MOF808 material is not stable at temperatures above 200 °C, this catalyst was only re-characterised as is.

Figure 6: Conversion of furfural and yields of C8 and C13 product molecules depending on TOS with mdAl₂O₃-ext at 120 °C.

Table III shows the properties of the regenerated catalysts. Most regenerated materials had similar surface areas as measured in the fresh catalysts; except the HT2 catalysts that had a significant decrease in surface area. The low temperature basicity of the regenerated catalysts was relatively similar to that measured in the fresh catalysts. On the other hand, the high temperature basicity decreased significantly for the HT2 and mdAl₂O₃ catalysts. These results indicate the robustness of the catalysts, in particular for the low temperature cross-condensation after regeneration. Future work will further validate the re-use of regenerated catalysts under flow in order to assess the suitability of the materials for a scaled up process.

Figure 7: mdAl₂O₃-ext catalyst before (fresh, left) and after (spent, right) test of cross-condensation of FUR and ACE.

Table III: Properties of regenerated catalysts: BET surface area and basicity in terms of CO₂ uptake

Regenerated catalysts	BET surface area (m ² /g)	CO ₂ uptake <200 °C (μmol/g)	CO ₂ uptake 200-500 °C (μmol/g)
KMG30	92	116	826
HT2	35	84	346
MOF808	n.d.	9.8	n.a.
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -ext	170	46	566
mdAl ₂ O ₃ -tri	204	66	568

3.3 High temperature self-condensation of cyclopentanone

Three catalysts were tested for their activity on the self-condensation of cyclopentanone: KMG30, HT2 and mdAl₂O₃-tri. In order to evaluate the activity and product distribution over time using KMG30, this catalyst was first tested at a reaction temperature of 320 °C using a space velocity of 6.0 mmol g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ for 90 h on stream (TOS).

Figure 8 shows the CPO conversion and C10 and C15 product yields using KMG30 at four different TOS. The graph shows that the CPO conversion decreased from 59 % to 18 % during 89 h TOS. In every 24 h interval, the conversion decreased between 28 and 37 %. This causes a nearly 70 % lower conversion.

Figure 8: Conversion of CPO and yields of the C10 and C15 product molecules depending on TOS during the CPO self-condensation with KMG30 at 320 °C.

The yields of the C10 products, which are mainly 2-cyclopentylidenecyclopentanone (DCPOe) and minor amounts of 2-cyclopentylcyclopentanone (DCPO), started with 24 % in the first sample and decreased after 42 h TOS and remained then stable at 18 % yield. The yield of the C15 products behaved differently. C15 yield decreased in the same way as the conversion from 35 % to no yield after 89 h TOS. The C15 products were different isomers of 2,4-dicyclopentyl-cyclopentanone (TCPO), 2-cyclopentylidene-4-cyclopentylcyclopentanone (TCPOe). The spent catalyst was dark brown to black compared to the nearly white fresh catalyst.

Figure 9: Conversion of CPO and yields of C10 and C15 products at various temperatures and TOS with KMG30 catalyst.

The next step was to test the effect of both temperature and TOS to evaluate how a subsequent temperature increase during the TOS affected the catalyst activity. Therefore, the following test with fresh KMG30 started at 280 °C and after about 18 h TOS, the temperature was increased to 320 °C. Another 24 h later, the temperature was increased to 360 °C. The results are shown in Figure 9. The first sample was taken after 18 h at 280 °C reaction temperature, the second and third samples were taken 24 h after reaching 320 and 360 °C, respectively. The conversion at all three reaction temperatures was in the range of 35 %. The increasing temperature helped to minimize the negative influence of the TOS on the conversion of CPO in the synthesis as previously seen in Figure 8. The yield of C15 product molecules as named above seemed to depend mostly on the reaction temperature. A significant yield above 10 % was only observed at the highest reaction temperature of 360 °C. Therefore, the production of the C10 product molecules remains stable and are the main product of the synthesis. Even at low TOS when the C15 molecule was the main product in the previous test, at 280 °C only bicyclic molecules were formed.

This procedure was identically used to test the mdAl₂O₃-tri catalyst for the gas phase self-condensation of CPO. The results are shown in Figure 10. Compared to KMG30, all three parameters, the CPO conversion, the yield of the C10 and the C15 molecules, were relatively more stable over the test. The conversion was 45 % after 18 h TOS at 280 °C. After 42 h TOS, the conversion decreased to 40 % and to 39 % after 66 h TOS. The yields of the C10 and C15 molecules only slightly decreased. The C10 molecules have a yield of 28 % at 280 °C and 23 % at 360 °C, which is a decrease of 15 %. The yield of the C15 molecules behaved similar with 19 % at 280 °C and 16 %

at 360 °C. The decrease here was 16 % compared to the initial value. The colour of the catalyst changed as observed before with the KMG30 catalyst from white to nearly black after use.

Figure 10: Conversion of CPO and yields of C10 and C15 products at various temperatures and TOS with mdAl₂O₃-tri catalyst.

Hydrotalcite (HT2) was also tested in the same procedure. Also here a change of colour from white for the fresh catalyst to black after use was observed. The conversion of CPO slightly increased with temperature increase. But compared to the doped alumina catalyst, the yield of C15 molecules was only 10 % after 18 h at 280 °C. At higher TOS, the yield of C15 molecules decreased subsequently to 3 % and then to 0 %, even though the temperature was increased to 320 and 360 °C.

4 CONCLUSIONS & OUTLOOK

This work focused on the evaluation of the performance of base catalysts for the production of C8-C13 jet fuel precursors via condensation of furfural and cyclopentanone. Three types of catalysts were identified during screening of a model reaction and formed structures (pellets, extrudates) of the catalysts produced for testing in fixed bed reactors. Two operation regimes were assessed in this study: low temperature (80-120 °C/liquid phase) cross-condensation of furfural with acetone, and high temperature (280-360 °C/gas phase) self-condensation of cyclopentanone.

For the low temperature process, a hydrotalcite and a metal-organic-framework type of catalysts were most active, robust and stable up to 53 h, providing high conversions (> 85 %) and favouring the formation of C13 over C8 molecules.

For the high temperature process, metal doped alumina catalysts were most active, providing stable conversion (40-45 %) and a product distribution favouring C10 over C15 molecules but with stable ratios between C10 and C15 yields. The conversions and yields have the potential to be optimised by varying the space velocity and reaction temperature.

The two process regimes (low and high temperature) can provide flexibility in the production of bio-based hydrocarbons for jet fuel production. Deactivation of the catalysts was observed due to strong carbon adsorption which was addressed through calcination for regeneration. Future work will focus on the evaluation of the stability of regenerated catalysts and the subsequent hydrotreatment

of the products from condensation.

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6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

- This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101006618. The present publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.
- K. Dussan, A. van Zomeren and J.W. van Hal thank Petra Bonouvrie, Raghavendra Sumbharaju, Michiel

Hoek, Ron van der Laan, Ben van Egmond, Karina Vogelpoel-de Wit, Gertjan Herder and Marc Crockatt for their contributions.

- M. Peters and A. Kraft thank C. Graf and C. Harms for their support on the experimental work and A. Fastabend and T. Ombeck for the analytical support.
- S. Scalzullo (Johnson Matthey) would like to thank Przemyslaw Magdziarz, Matthew Rose, Alex Oje, Edward Bilbé, Emma Softley and Rob Fletcher for their support with material characterisation, and Elena Blanco for her support with pellet preparation.

